

PID:37076-Jule_Drewalowski- sampling_Kristineberg

Version 1

Description

During my visit in Kristineberg, I will collect pipefish samples that will be used for DNA sequencing. I will re-sequence whole-genomes for 15 individuals of *Syngnathus typhle* and 15 individuals of *Nerophis ophidion*. Once sequenced, the raw data needs to be deposited in a public repository and so does the resulting processed data. I will mainly be using ENA for sequencing data and ERDA (openly accessible data archive of the University of Copenhagen) for all associated meta-data and resulting analyses.

Funder

Grant

Researchers

Jule Drewalowski (0009-0000-8718-2377)

Organizations
University of Copenhagen

1. Main Info

Title of Plan: [PID:37076-Jule_Drewalowski-sampling_Kristineberg](#)

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Researchers:

[Jule Drewalowski \(0009-0000-8718-2377\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Copenhagen](#)

Contact: [Drewalowski Jule \(jule.drewalowski@bio.ku.dk\)](#)

Access: [Public](#)

2. Ethics

Introduction:

The activity will involve sampling of 30 local pipefishes. I am in contact with the Animal Ethics Officer at Kristineberg, who assured me that the proposed numbers and species are reasonable. Permits are in order. I took the relevant courses for animal ethics training and laboratory animal science to work with vertebrates for research purposes in Sweden. The pipefish will be killed immediately after sampling from the wild.

3. Dataset descriptions

Introduction:

The sampled fishes will be used for whole genome re-sequencing. Data for 30 genomes, 15 for each species, will be sequenced using Illumina.

Descriptions

AQUASERV | Molecular Biology & Omics | sequencing

Template: AQUASERV | Molecular Biology & Omics | sequencing

Type: Dataset

1 Summary

1.1 dataset type

1.1.1 Please specify the dataset type

WGS of 2 pipefish species (*Syngnathus typhle*, *Nerophis ophidion*) for 15 individuals of each species

2 Your research data

2.1 Sequencing machine details

2.1.1 Sequencing chemistry / kits used

DNA extraction: DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit, dsDNA Quantitation, high sensitivity
Library preparation: Illumina DNA PCR-Free Prep (Tagmentation), ssDNA Quantitation, IDT for Illumina DNA/RNA UD Indexes Set A (Tagmentation)

2.2 General type of data

2.2.1 additional information about your dataset

WGS of rather low coverage because high quality reference genomes for both species are available.

2.3 Type of data (format)

2.3.1 Data format

4TB of raw reads (13332 M reads). This is 2 x 25B PE150 lanes on Illumina NovaSeq X

2.4 Documentation and data quality

2.4.1 How will the data be documented and described/analysed? Please specify which type of documentation record are you planning to use (e.g. paper or electronic labbook, online resource) and which software are you planning to analyse your data with

An electronic lab book will be used for documenting progress and status of each sample. This allows for version control and automatic backups. The raw sequencing data will be demultiplexed with the software bcl2fastq and trimmed with fastp. VCFtools and Samtools will be used for mapping, sorting, variant calling and variant filtering. ANGSD will be used to perform population genetic analyses.

2.5 Storage and Backup

2.5.1 Do you use any intermediate storage devices? Please describe your backup plan.

All raw data and analysis outputs will be stored and backed up using the University of Copenhagen's data storage system ERDA. Additionally raw data and major/final steps of the analysis will be backed up on external hard drives. While analyzing the data, it will additionally be stored on Computerome, the HPC cluster of Copenhagen's university.

2.6 Accessibility and long-term storage

2.6.1 Long term data storage - database

ENA

2.6.2 Accession number

(will be filled in later)

2.7 Your metadata

2.7.1 Metadata format

Metadata on the samples such as weight, length, species, sampling information (date, location, salinity, temperature) will be stored in a spreadsheet. This will then be complemented with metadata extracted from the sequencing data. Additionally, photos of each specimen will be taken. Various file formats of metadata resulting from the different analyses will be available as well.

2.7.2 How is your metadata connected to the research data

From the initial point of sampling, each individual will be assigned with a unique ID, that will be used throughout the whole project.

2.7.3 Metadata storage

All meta data will be stored and backed up using the University of Copenhagen's data storage system ERDA. (URL + DOI will be provided once data is available)

3 Licence/embargo

3.2 Embargo on data release

3.2.1 Embargo details

No embargo, data will be available as soon as it is generated

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